

Computer Science Education of Public Universities in Kabul versus Required Competencies in the Local Job Market

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Abstract

One of the common challenges for computer science graduates is market-oriented skills and competencies. Graduates are feeling the gap between curriculum contents and required skills of the job market. No research has been done to provide reliable information that in which extent the graduates of public universities in Kabul city of Afghanistan satisfy the industries- and job-market requirements. Our work is devoted to empirically investigate the required computer science skills and competencies in the job-market of Kabul city and academic curriculum in the public universities of Kabul city. We choose a case-study based research method to bridge the gap between academic curriculum and required job skills in the local- market and industries. The result of our study describes to what extent the current curriculum, and teaching methods reflect the required skills of the local job market.

Keywords: Curriculum, Competencies, Job-market, Graduates Skills, Skills Gap

1. Introduction

Computer Science applications and services are new and highly demanded in private and public sectors of Afghanistan. Therefore, there is huge demand for computer science specialists in the local job market. In some areas, computer science specialists from foreign countries are called for working with highly paid salaries. On the other hand, every year a large number of students are graduated from Afghanistan public universities in the field of computer science. Students who graduated from universities enter a competitive job market to work as professional workers in order to deliver qualified job. The success of the graduates depends on matching of computer science curriculum and the required skills in the local job-market [1].

Commonly, there is a gap between academic education and job-market environments. Students at universities are not experienced with the real-life practices as they are doing in industries and job-market. Because of the dynamic situation of computer science job-market, the linkage between computer science curriculum and the required skills of job-market need continues academic and professional studies in all around the world. Academic institutions and industries are like two pillars for the development of society and they cannot be isolated from each other. Because universities provide qualified, skilled, and professional human resource to the industries and industries provide job opportunities for these graduates. Mostly, graduates feel that the studied materials are irrelevant to the practical work experience. Many countries around the world considered this problem and studied how to bridge the gap between academic education and industries in order to bridge between university curriculum and required job-market skills and competencies. Public universities in Afghanistan need to establish such mutual relation between computer science curriculum and the required skills in the job market.

As we mentioned earlier, it is not clear that to what extend the information technology (IT) curriculum, teaching methodologies, and tools reflect the need for required skills in the IT industries of Afghanistan. Related to this problem, the aim of this paper is to study the relationship between computer science curriculum in Kabul public universities and IT job-market requirements. The result of our study provides useful and realistic information on the relevancy of computer science education in Kabul public universities and the required skills in computer

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science IT job-market in Afghanistan. Our empirical study relies on data collection and analysis from the local market and computer science institutions in public universities. Our aim is refined to the main research question of our paper, namely:

- How to provide a mutual relationship between the computer science curriculum and the required skills in the local job market?

To establish a separation of concerns, the main research question is divided into the following sub questions:

- i. What are the required IT skills in the local market that are missed in the public IT institutions?
- ii. What is the gap between teaching methods and IT job-market skills?
- iii. Which topics in the computer science curriculum are irrelevant to real-life practices in the IT job market?
- iv. What are the main challenges for IT graduates from public universities when enter into IT job-market?
- v. What are the sectors in which foreign IT specialists are working?

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II provides related works. Section III describes our case study design, data collection and analysis procedures. In Section IV we present the results of our research and evaluation of its validity. Finally, Section V concludes this paper by summarizing the research work, giving the contributions achieved.

2.Related Works

Information Technology institutions have an important role in improving economy and social potential of nations [2]. Therefore, computer science graduates' skills and abilities are vital factors in the development of societies. If computer science courses are taught properly, then the graduates are able to be creative, critical thinkers and be skilled in applying the learned theories for solving practical problems in different contexts. Furthermore, computer science courses enable students to be competitive in the job market for positions that require professional and deep skills [3]. Generally, skills can be categorized into hard and soft skills. Hard skills refer to technical, professional, and job-specific skills [4]. Soft skills are non-technical skills that include the attitudes and characteristics related to personality and behaviors of peoples [5]. Soft skills include problem solving, communication, team working, leadership, and cooperative skills [6], [7]. Hard skills are the basic and essential requirements for job and soft skills are required for career development. In another word, the hard skills are required during the employment and soft skills are important during the job performance [8]. According to the report conducted by (World Bank, 2008) Middle East and North Africa countries need to realize the potential of reforming education to include soft skills.

There are many factors that cause the gap between curriculum and job market skills. One of the factors is the rapid changes and development of IT technologies that make the required skills challenging and require continuous improvement. Consequently, it makes the process of curriculum development challenging for academic intuitions and curriculum developers [9], [10]. Besides the rapid changes in technology, there are other factors such as the static nature of IT curriculum, instructor training, dynamic nature of job market, changing pattern of working in industries, and teaching methodology. All these factors increase the gap between curriculum and job market skills [11]. The extent and life span of the gap depend on how fast universities adjust and update their curriculum [11]. Educational, pedagogical, and economic factors emphasize the computer education to be based on the market skills and competencies [12].

The skill gap is the difference between what is required or expected and what we actually get [13]. The consequences of the skill gap in the IT industries and universities cause the importation of skilled workers from other countries and waste of human resources from the home country [13]. This gap strongly affects the

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economy of the country, particularly that government schools and university education are free of cost in Afghanistan. Developing better IT curriculum has a significant role in bridging the skill gap.

Although, quality assurance policy improves the innovative teaching, and employment of the graduates [14], [15]. However, identifying the required skills of the IT job market is a challenging task due to the factors such as the rapid development in technologies and the continuous changes in the evolvement of these technologies in the IT sector [9]. Therefore, it requires an empirical research to be conducted in order to manage the gap between curriculum and job market skills.

Related to Afghanistan, in the last 15 years the number of computer science graduates increased rapidly. However, the shortage of computer science-related skills has been observed in the local job market and industries. The gap that exists between what is taught at universities and the skills required to perform on a job is so wide that a high percentage of young graduates are said to be unemployable for lack of needed skills. Based on our literature, regardless of some subjective discussion on the topic, no holistic research has been conducted to provide dependable information that in which extent the Afghanistan university graduates fulfill the industries and job market requirements. Therefore, wide and universal research is required to be done and the fact of how much the job markets are satisfied with skills and competencies Afghan universities' graduates

3. Research Methodology

The connection between the computer science curriculum and job-market skills requires empirical study and investigation. Therefore, we choose a case-study based research method [16] to evaluate mutual relationship between computer science curriculum and required skills in the local job market. A case study is an empirical inquiry that draws on the source of evidence to investigate a subject within its real-life context. A case study consists of these main phases: case-study design, data collection procedure, data analysis procedure, data validity procedure, and reporting [16]. In this section, we describe the research design, data collection, data analysis, and data validity.

Case Study Design

We answer our research questions with our case-study data collection and analysis. The mutual relationship between the computer science curriculum and the required skills in the local job-market is selected as a case for our study with holistic design [16]. The subject for our study is the gap between computer science curriculum and the required skills of the local job market.

Data Collection Procedures

For collecting data, we conduct interviews and questionnaires methods. The population of this study was selected from three categories. The first category is the graduates from the four public universities of Kabul city. The second category is IT experts working in IT industries such as banks, telecommunication companies, and software houses in the local market. The third category is the head of departments and academic staff of public computer science institutions in Kabul city. We define three different sets of questions to collect the related data. The questions for graduate students were distributed among 45 graduates working in different companies such as telecommunication, banks, mobile companies, and software houses. IT expert questions were distributed to 33 IT experts working in different positions of IT-related jobs. The third group of questions was distributed in computer science institutions of public universities among 15 department heads, senior lecturers, and curriculum committee members. All the targeted samples were computer science specialists and working for IT-related jobs. The questionnaires are carefully derived from the research questions listed in Section II.

Analysis of Procedure

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The main goal of the analysis is to investigate the relationship between computer science curriculum and the job-market skills and reveal the gap between them. To achieve our goal, we analyze the collected data in the following steps:

- i. First, we code the collected data using the Microsoft Excel sheet.
- ii. Second, we formulate a set of themes that group the related codes. Each theme belongs to one of our research questions.
- iii. We read all the texts in the collected data and mark where the codes fit into the themes.
- iv. Results are derived from each theme and presented.

Table I shows our predefined themes and a brief description from which a corresponding theme is derived.

Table I: Themes and Themes description

Theme	Theme Description
Market Required Skills	Specify the required skills for IT in the local market.
Missing Skills	Specify the skills that IT experts and graduates mentioned as missing skills for IT graduates
Foreign Workers Skills	Job market skills that foreign workers have
Skills in IT Curriculum	Current skills in the IT curriculum
Teaching Methodology	The current teaching methodologies in departments.
Irrelevant Topics	Irrelevant topics in the curriculums
Graduates Challenges	The challenges for graduates when they enter the local job market.

The above themes are derived from our research questions. Table II shows the coding results for the questionnaire with IT experts and graduates. Codes are sorted based on their value.

Table II: Table of IT experts and graduates coding results

Themes / Codes	Sources	No. of Sources
1. Market Required Skills		
Software development	IT Experts + Graduates	30+21= 51
Web development	IT Experts + Graduates	25+19= 44
Database management & administration	IT Experts + Graduates	20+17= 37
Network administration	IT Experts + Graduates	13+23= 36
Network security	IT Experts + Graduates	15+14= 29
Practical skills and work with new technologies	IT Experts + Graduates	15+13= 28
Mobile programming	IT Experts + Graduates	5+9= 14
Team working & communication skills	IT Experts	12
System analysis & design	IT Experts + Graduates	9+3= 12
Project management	Graduates	12
Dot net programming development	IT Experts	11
Solving complex problems	IT Experts	10
Oracle database	IT Experts	9
Branch connectivity	IT Experts	9
In-depth knowledge of Networking	IT Experts	8
Data science & analysis	IT Experts	7
IT consultancy	IT Experts	7
Information system security	IT Experts	5
Business process management	IT Experts	5
Virtualization	IT Experts	4
Troubleshooting	IT Experts	2
2. Missing Skills		
Practical work & experiences of new & existing technologies	IT Experts + Graduates	23+19= 42
Ability to learn new technologies	IT Experts + Graduates	14+14= 28
Business process management	IT Experts + Graduates	9+13= 22
Information security	IT Experts + Graduates	13+9= 22

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Cryptography & network security	IT Experts + Graduates	13+8= 21
Self-learning skill	IT Experts + Graduates	5+13= 18
Advance database development	IT Experts	18
Communication skills	IT Experts + Graduates	5+11= 16
Software development projects	IT Experts	16
Artificial intelligence	IT Experts + Graduates	5+10= 15
Team working skills	Graduates	15
Machine learning	IT Experts + Graduates	7+6= 13
Integration and interoperability	IT Experts	12
Ethical hacking	IT Experts	10
Mobile applications development	IT Experts	8
English language skills	Graduates	7
Dot net framework	IT Experts	7
Problem solving skills	IT Experts	7
ERP Management	IT Experts	6
Data science and analysis	IT Experts	6
Software testing	IT Experts	5
Cloud computing	IT Experts	5
Voice detection and recognition	IT Experts	3
Virtualization technology	IT Experts	2
3. Foreign Workers Skills		
High technical problem analysis, evaluation & solving	IT Experts + Graduates	15+12= 27
Practical work	IT Experts + Graduates	10+17= 27
Software project planning & management	IT Experts + Graduates	10+12= 22
Software development & integration	IT Experts	21
Good practical knowledge of the working environment	IT Experts + Graduates	5+13= 18
Database experts	IT Experts	17
Cybersecurity	IT Experts	12
Advance team working & communication skills	IT Experts	12
Working with new & latest technology	IT Experts	11
Technical issues that require experiences of a long period of time	IT Experts	10
System analysis & development	IT Experts	10
Dot net applications	IT Experts	9
Open-source technologies	IT Experts	8
Policy development	IT Experts	8
Ethical hacking	IT Experts	7
Leading and crucial IT positions	IT Experts	7
Implementing WAN technologies	IT Experts	7
Advanced hardware and software troubleshooting	IT Experts	6
Mobile applications	IT Experts	6
Enterprise understanding	IT Experts	4
Data science	IT Experts	4
Artificial intelligence	IT Experts	3
Virtualizations	IT Experts	3
Critical thinking	IT Experts	2
4. Teaching Methodology		
Teaching materials include less amount of practical work	Graduates	21
Teaching is not project based	Graduates	19
Lower student contributions during teaching	Graduates	18
Not enough discussion during teaching	Graduates	16

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Team & group working is less	Graduates	12
Some lessons are repeated between different courses	Graduates	9
5. Irrelevant Topics		
History	Graduates	21
Most topics of Physics	Graduates	16
General mathematics	Graduates	13
Repeated topics in different subjects	Graduates	10
Some topics are old and not updated	Graduates	7
Topics are mentioned but not practically shown		5
6. Graduates Challenges		
Practical knowledge & experiences	IT Experts + Graduates	30+7= 37
Practical knowledge of new technologies	IT Experts + Graduates	15+17= 32
Knowledge of market and customer requirements	IT Experts + Graduates	6+22= 28
Lack of deep understanding in the concerned domain	IT Experts + Graduates	6+17= 23
Communication skills	IT Experts + Graduates	11+12= 23
Difference between curriculum and market	IT Experts	16
Graduates are not up to date	Graduates	14
Graduates have a team working skill problem	Graduates	13
English language	Graduates	13
Changing market demand	IT Experts	8
Not familiar with project work	IT Experts	7
Some theories & concepts are not related to our work	Graduates	6
Graduates have no internship opportunities	Graduates	5
High expectations in the field of IT	IT Experts	4
Lack of knowledge about the local market technology	IT Experts	3
Lack of internship opportunity	IT Experts	2

Table III shows the coding results for the interview and questionnaire with the academic staff of computer science institutions in four public university of Kabul city.

Table III: Table of IT curriculum coding results

Themes / Codes	No. of Sources
1: Skills in Curriculum	
Web design and development	6
Network administration	5
Software development	5
Database administration	4
Design and develop mobile applications	4
Design and develop desktop applications	3
Work in a team of software developers	3
Projects management	2
Network security	2
Information systems	1
Identify, formulate, and solve engineering problems	1
Life-long learning	1
Problem solving	1
Computer architecture & electronics	1
2: Missing Skills in Curriculum	
Practical skills	5
Market oriented frameworks	3

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Data science	3
Artificial intelligence	2
iOS mobile application development	1
Robotics	1
Internet of things	1
Machine learning	1
Data mining	1
Big data	1
Soft-skill	1
3: Curriculum Alignment with OBE	
The curriculum follows OBE guidelines	4
Only in the course & learning objectives & outcome	2
It is not exactly designed based on OBE	2
We are planning in the future	1
4: Market Study for Curriculum	
The curriculum is based on the market need	7
The curriculum is based on international standards	6
Sometimes the curriculum lacks new need of the market	2
The curriculum is not fully developed based on market study	1
5: Graduates Feedback for Curriculum	
The curriculum is based on graduates feedback	6
To some extent Curriculum is based on the graduate's feedback	4
No, the curriculum is not on the graduate's feedback	3
6: Teaching & IT Competencies	
Lack of equipment for practical work	4
A large number of students in the class	4
Lack of coordination between the IT market and universities	4
Quickly changes in market demands	3
Lack of capacity building and training programs	2
Teaching methodology matches IT competencies	1
Teaching is according to curriculum	1
Teaching consider IT market demand	1
Teaching materials are updated	1
Students develop their own projects	1
Students learn how to collaborate in a team	1
The contents are not so much align with the market needs	1
Less amount of teaching materials	1
No visible relationship between teaching methodology & local market need	1
Market need is not assessed for teaching	1
Unavailability of IT-job market assessment policy	1

Codes are sorted based on their value and then, we review every theme separately and draw conclusions.

Validity procedures

For improving the data validity, we carefully design our study by implementing the qualitative-investigation measures and data- validity rules in all phases of the case study. For ensuring construct validity, we induce our data collection questions from our research question and the research questions are strongly related to the objectives of our study. For ensuring internal validity that removes the effect of external factors, we carefully developed our data collection questions in such a way that are very clear and there is no ambiguity in the text of questions. During the analysis, we coded the collected data and we use themes to categorize and generalize the findings.

4. Results

As mentioned earlier, our goal is to study the relationship between computer science curriculum in Kabul public universities and the job-market requirements. We assess the status of computer science education and the job-market requirements to provide useful and realistic information on the relevancy of computer science education in Kabul public universities and skills and competencies required in the local job-market in Afghanistan. For achieving this goal, we design an empirical study that relies on data collection and analysis from the local market and computer science institutions in public universities. For each of our research questions, we determine a corresponding theme. The results presented in Table II and Table III help institution to develop curriculum that has mutual relationship of computer science education in public universities and the required skills and competencies in the job-market in Afghanistan. From Table II and Table III, we can answer our research questions.

Based on the results of our study, the most important skills in the local job-market depend on the ability of graduates in software development, web development, database administration, network security and administration. Working with new technology, team working, communication skills, and project management are also the required skills in the local job market. Computer science competencies require the knowledge, skills, experiences, and abilities that are needed for graduates to perform successfully in the job market. These competencies include personal effectiveness, academic knowledge, workplace ability, technical ability, and theoretical knowledge.

The results in Table II indicate that the most importing missing skills among computer science graduates from public universities are practical experiences of new and existing technologies, advance database development, mobile application development, artificial intelligence, self-learning skill, team working and communication skills. Business process management, information- and network security, ethical hacking, project management, and data science and analysis are mentioned as missed skills among computer science graduates.

The collected data from the graduates of public universities indicate that the teaching materials include less amount of practical work and teaching is not project based. The lower contribution of students and the low level of discussion during teaching also are weak points in the teaching methodology. The graduates indicate that the education needs to include team working and it should address more complex and creative tasks that require critical thinking about practical problems using computer technologies. The teaching methods need to improve both the quality of student knowledge and practical skills in order to improve student potential and self-confidence. The academic staff point to some problems that affect the quality of teaching. These problems include shortage of equipment for practical work, large number of students in classes, and lack of capacity building and training programs for instructors.

The graduates also pointed to some irrelevant subjects in the computer science curriculum of public universities. These subjects include most topics in physics, general mathematics and contemporary history. Repeated topics in different subjects, old and not updated topics, and topics that just mentioned by instructors and not practically shown are other issues that are mentioned by the graduates.

Based on our results the main challenges for computer science graduates from public universities are practical knowledge and experiences, the difference between curriculum and market skills, communication skills, project management skill, and lack of deep understanding in concerned domain. The rapid changes in computer technologies and high expectations in the field of computer science cause continuous pressure on the graduates in order to acquire new skills and knowledge.

Based on the collected data from the graduates and computer science experts, the foreign workers have extra skills in technical problem analysis and solving, software development and integration, database administration,

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cybersecurity, working with new technology, and software project planning and management. They have an efficient team working and communication skills, policy development, and critical thinking skills.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of our study, the large amount for the gap between computer science education in public universities and the required skills and competencies in the local job market is in the delivery of the materials and teaching methodologies. For decreasing this gap, computer science education in the public universities must evolve in both teaching materials and methodologies. Currently the curriculums and teaching methodologies lack sufficient practical work, team working, and teaching is not project based. Furthermore, the lower contribution of students and the low level of discussion during teaching are weak points in the teaching methodology. The curriculum contents and teaching methodologies in public universities need to address more complex and inventive tasks that require critical thinking for solving practical problems using computer technologies. To cope with the rapid and continuous changes in computer technologies and high expectations of the field of computer science, computer science institutions in the public universities need to develop effective and pedagogical teaching materials and methodologies that improve the graduate's self-learning. The professional courses should include project-based practical work and must facilitate team-based tasks. Computer science institutions also need to involve their students in the local industries during their study through internships programs and guide students to realize the connection between what they are learning and solutions to the real-world practical problems. This study was limited in that it was carried out within public universities in one city.

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